

Speech Act in The Learning Process of a Bilingual School

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Abstract

This research aims to explain (1) Types of speech acts used by teachers in the learning process at Canggu Community School, Bali (2) Types of speech acts used by teachers in the learning process at the school, and (3) Speech act functions that teachers in the school use. This research data were collected from teachers' speech in the learning process at Canggu Community School. The data were collected in spoken language and transcribed to written language. Recording and note-taking techniques were used to collect the data. The results of the analysis are presented using formal and informal methods. The results of the analysis show that (1) the types of speech acts of locution, illocution, and perlocution were also found almost in every teacher's speech in the learning process at Canggu Community School (2) The forms of teacher speech acts found in the learning process at Canggu Community School are: 5 declarative utterances, 11 interrogative utterances, and seven imperative utterances (3) The speech act functions found in the learning process at Canggu Community School are: 6 assertive utterances, ten directive utterances, three commissive utterances, five expressive utterances, and three declarative utterances.

1. Introduction

The learning process cannot be separated from using language as an introduction (Ndiaye & Camaco, 2021). In a speech, there are utterances spoken by the speaker to the speech partner with a

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specific purpose and aim. Saeed (2022) states that utterance is a speech formed from writing or conversation in a language. Thus, the utterance results from speaking both in oral and written form, with a specific purpose and aim.

One form of utterance in a language can be seen in a study called speech acts (Ghorbani, 2020). The speech act is part of the pragmatic field of science, which contains interpretations of a speech spoken by a speaker to his speech partner. Abdul (2004: 16) states that speech acts can be interpreted as an individual phenomenon and to achieve the desired purpose in speech requires the ability of the language of the speaker to deal with a particular situation. The understanding of the speech act shows that the speech act is an attempt to convey the utterance carried out by the speaker so that the speech partner can interpret well the intent and purpose of the utterance (Fishman, 1970; Hudson, 1996; Spolsky, 1998; Chambers, 2007).

Speech act theory, in general, can be divided into three parts: locutionary speech acts, illocutionary speech acts, and perlocutionary speech acts (Sbisà, 2009; Ariyaningsih, 2020; Sani et al., 2020; Sumarta et al., 2022). The three parts of speech act have differences in interpreting an utterance uttered by the speaker. Locutionary acts are speech acts that contain limited speech only to convey information to the speech partner without any other intention desired by the speaker. Illocutionary acts are speech acts that contain utterances with meanings and intentions implied in them, so the speech partner needs to interpret the purpose of the utterances conveyed by the speaker. Perlocutionary acts contain utterances spoken by the speaker to the speech partner so that the speech partner takes action based on the utterance uttered by the speaker.

Types of Speech Acts

Austin (1962) explains that a speech act has meaning in context and that meaning can be categorized into meaning of locution, illocution, and perlocution. Based on this, Austin distinguishes or classifies speech acts into three types based on their power, including Localization (Lectonary act), which is the relation of a topic with one statement in an expression, similar to the relationship 'main' with 'predicate 'or' topic 'and explanation in syntax (Searle: 1969). Illocutionary act, namely the pronunciation of a statement, offer, promise of questions, etc. Perlocutionary act, which is the result or effect caused by the expression on the listener, according to the situation and condition of the pronunciation of the sentence. The response is not only in the form of words but also in the form of actions or actions. The speaker can intentionally or unintentionally create this effect or influence.

Forms of Speech Acts

Linguistic aspects of speech form part of the overall communication activities and are called speech acts (Duranti, 2011). Wijana & Putu (2004) suggests that speech acts can be realized with direct or indirect *declarative, interrogative, and imperative* modes of speech with a literal or non-literal meaning (Cf. Hock & Joseph, 2019).

Functions of Speech Act

Searle (1969) states that based on their function, speech acts can be distinguished from assertive, directive, expressive, commissive, and declaration speech acts. (1) *Assertiveness*: intends to convey something related to the truth of a proposition or statement that is expressed, for example, declaring to accept or reject, propose, brag, complain, submit an opinion, or report. (2) *Directives*: This illocution aims to ask the interlocutor to do something to produce an effect on the action taken by the speaker, for example, ordering, ordering, begging, demanding, or giving advice. (3) *Commissives*: illocution aims to convey

something that is bound to act in the future, for example, promising or offering. (4) *Expressives*: the function of this illocution is to reveal or express the psychological attitude of the speaker towards the state implicit in the illocution, for example, to say thank you, congratulate, apologize, criticize, praise, praise, express condolences, and so on. (5) *Declarations*: The function of this illocution is to express statements that the success of the implementation appears in conformity with the reality of the action, for example, resigning, baptizing, firing, naming, dropping punishment, isolating or disposing of, appointing (employees), etc.

2. Materials and Methods

The data in this study are in the form of oral conversation discourse transcribed in the form of written data. Thus, the recorded data of teachers' speech in the learning process at Canggus Community School in the form of oral data is then transcribed into written data. The utterances are produced by the teacher and students when dialoguing, interacting, and communicating in class learning. Data were analyzed using the types of speech act theory (Austin, 1962), the forms of speech act theory (Wijana & Putu, 2004), and the functions of speech act theory (Searle, 1969).

3. Results and Discussions

Types of Speech Acts

Based on the type, speech acts are divided into locution, illocution, and perlocution. The following are examples of the types of speech acts that are contained in teacher speech in the learning process at Canggus Community School:

a) Data (MMd -13)

The following data below shows the speech between the teacher and students that occurred in the class. The following is presented speech data of teachers and students:

Teacher : *Silakan you can do this dengan teman sebangku mu!* (Please, you can do this with your seatmate!)

Student : *All right*

Teacher teaching based on sentence data above, "*Silakan you can do this dengan teman sebangku mu!*", is an imperative sentence sent by the teacher to students. The sentence used aims to get people to do something as instructed by the speaker. Imperative sentences are usually used in conjunction with politeness *ayo, biar, hendaknya, mohon, silakan, tolong, dan coba* (Rahardi, 2007, p. 83; Rose, 2005). Speech acts delivered by the teacher to students in the form of localized speech acts in the form of imperative sentences sent to inform something information in the form of orders told the opposite speaker. This teacher's speech also contains illocutionary speech acts, which are not only informative, but there is a certain tendency to do something that is through the imperative sentences of the order. The form of the word "please" in the speech has the meaning of try or help (to smooth the order or invitation). The purpose and purpose of the request is the teacher wants students to carry out discussions with their peers to discuss persuasive texts. At the same time, the perlocution effect produced by teacher speech is by giving orders for students to do the assignments given with their peers. Speech partner responses are students who understand and understand the task well through responses that are taught by students. This can be seen from the responses of students who say, "all right."

b) Data (MD-11)

The data below shows the speech between the teacher and students that occurred in the classroom. The following is presented speech data of teachers and students:

Teacher : *Ayo kita lihat video ini!* (Let us look at this video)

In the teacher's speech data 11, the sentence "*Ayo kita lihat video ini!*" The above contains an imperative invitation sentence usually used with a modesty sign *ayo, biar, mari, harap, hendaknya, dan hendaklah* (Rahardi, 2007, p. 82). The form of the word "come on" has the meaning of an appeal to invite or give encouragement. Data 11 also contains locus speech acts in the form of information containing an invitation to do something. Illocutionary speech acts can also be analyzed in the speech through the teacher's command to invite them to do an activity together. The purpose and purpose are implied in the speech that the teacher wants to invite students to watch videos that become learning material together. At the same time, the speech acts of litigation that appear in the speech affect students in the form of their good and careful response in watching the video.

Forms of Speech Act

a) Declarative Speech Act

(1-7) Data MMy

The declarative sentence is the subject's sentence being the doer of the change to the sentence predicate (Rahardi, 2005, p. 75). In the data above there is a form of teacher illocutionary speech acts in the form of active declarative sentences as follows.

Teacher : *Ya saya akan menjelaskan lagi.* (Yes, I will explain it again.)

In the data (1-7) of learning process, the sentence is marked by an active verb marker, the subject in the speech is the actor and the predicate in the sentence uses the word "*menjelaskan*" (explain). The purpose of the speech is only to convey something informative to the speech partner. This utterance is uttered without a certain tendency to do something and influence the interlocutor. The teacher as a speaker, explains information related to the assignment that will be given to students. Students as speech partners respond to the information well and come to understand it after getting an explanation from the teacher. So from its use, the teacher's speech has a declarative speech act.

b) Interrogative Speech Acts

(1-6) Data MMd

A partial interrogative sentence is a question sentence intended to ask for some of the information in the question. This interrogative sentence uses question words whose types and types are determined based on the nature of the object intended by the partial interrogative sentence (Rahardi, 2005, p. 77; Rose, 2005). Examples of teacher utterances that contain partial interrogative sentences are as follows.

Teacher : *Apa contohnya sosmed? (What is an example of social media?)*

Students : *Instagram*

The utterance of data (1-6) is a partial interrogative sentence speech to ask for goods or things. This question sentence is marked by a grammatical marker in the form of a question word "apa" (what) and ends with a question mark. The teacher, as the speaker, intends to know the answer to a thing or situation to the speech partner. The response produced by the speech partner is in the form of verbal answers or cues. The teacher, as a speaker, asks students a term that has something to do with the material to be delivered. Students respond well to the teacher's speech and answer the teacher's questions verbally. So from its use, the teacher's speech has the form of interrogative speech acts.

c) Imperative Speech Act

(1-1) Data MMy

In imperative utterances, there are sentences that are used to get other people to do something as instructed by the speaker. In data 1, there are speeches using imperative sentences of demand, usually imperative sentences, which are very subtle, and are accompanied by sentences of speakers which are lower than the attitude of the speaker when speaking ordinary imperative sentences (Rahardi, 2005, p. 50). Data on the types of teacher speech forms in the form of imperative requests are explained below.

Teacher : *Kita mulai kelas hari ini. Silakan yang akan memimpin doa hari ini adalah Alma (We will start the class. Please, who will be the leader of the praying is Alma).*

Students : *Hi teman-teman mari kita berdoa. Berdoa dimulai! (Hi my friends; let us pray. Praying will be started)*

Speech on data (1-1) in the learning process contains the intention of governing the speaker in the hope that the speech partner implements the contents of the speech. The form of the word "please" in the speech has the meaning of try or help (to smooth the order or invitation). The speaker, the teacher, gives the order to the speech partner, the student, to lead the prayer. This is done to start the learning process. Students respond well to commands given by the teacher. The student invited other students to start praying together. From the use of these utterances, the purpose of the teacher's speech is imperative speech acts.

Functions of Speech Act

a) Assertive Speech Act

(1-15) Data MMy

Speech proposes she is one of the assertive speech acts that speakers use with their speech partners when communicating. The sentence that proposes a suggestion has the characteristic of presenting a better alternative. In essence, a sentence that proposes something undoubtedly shows an alternative. The interaction is the speech made by the speaker and the speech partner in the learning process. Data (1-15) shows the speech that contains the proposed speech acts.

Teacher : *Mischa kamu mau pindah kesini? Bawa kursinya ya!* (Mischa, do you want to move here? Bring the chair!)

Data (1-15) is categorized as assertive speech because the speech is binding on the truth of propositions or statements that are revealed in the learning process in class. The sentence is the utterance that proposes a suggestion expressed by the teacher that is addressed to students. In this speech, the teacher proposes to move positions to the students he appoints. The teacher felt the student did not understand the assignment, so he suggested the student sit close to him. The teacher expects feedback from students and students respond by following the teacher's instructions.

b) Directive Speech Act

(1-4) Data MMd

Commanding is one of the meanings contained in the directive illocutionary speech act of the speaker conveyed to the speech partner. The command sentence is usually up at the beginning and low at the end. The characteristic of the sentence structure is the use of particles *-lah* and an exclamation point (!). This is an ordinary command speech whose purpose is only to command it. Speech in the interaction intended here is the speech made by speakers and speech partners in the learning process in class. The following is the teacher's speech that shows the directive speech act.

Teacher : *Kelas 11, nanti kalau sudah ketemu bukunya, bukalah halaman teks D bahasa persuasif!* (Class 11, later, if the book has already found, open the page text D about persuasive!)

Students : *Sudah.* (Done)

These utterances are categorized as directive utterances because they aim to deliver an effect of actions taken by the interlocutor. The test is an expression that has the function of giving instructions by the teacher about the material to be discussed with students. The teacher as a speaker expects feedback or response from students. Students then respond well to speech that indicates they understand the command given.

C) Commissive Speech Acts

(1-4) Data MMy

Speakers use promising commissive speech acts to promise and express by undertaking all their actions so that the speech partner believes. Speech in data (1-4), including commissive promises with direct speech acts used by the speaker to express the speech directly so that the speech partner believes and is interested in the whole speech spoken by the speaker. The promising speech function promises we can see in the following data.

Teacher : *As you agreed at the beginning. Kita akan tetap melakukan tugas minggu lalu, saya akan menambahkan poin kalian disana yang ditandai warna hijau. Based what you did*

last week. (As you agreed at the beginning. We will continue last week's assignment, I will add your point, marked in green. Based on what you did last week.)

Data (1-4) only is not merely informative, but there is a certain tendency to convey something bound to act in the future. The purpose and goal are for the speaker, namely the teacher, to promise additional value to students. The teacher promised more value if he carried out the assignments given last week. Based on that promise, students, as opposed to speech, respond well and try to collect the assignment so that the speech has a commissive illocutionary speech act function.

d) Expressive Speech Acts

(1-18) Data MMy

Expressive speech to say thank you is a speech act that usually occurs because the speaker or the speech partner is willing to do what is asked or because of the kindness of the speaker who has given something to the speech partner or appreciate for what the speaker has done. The following speech data is an expression of expressive expressions of thanks.

Teacher : Ya, terima kasih. Selamat menikmati makan siang kalian. (Yup, thank you. Have a nice lunch)

Data (1-18) speech is informative and shows the teacher's psychological attitude as a speaker of the situation contained in the speech. The purpose and objective is the teacher as a speaker to express his gratitude and congratulations to his students. The teacher says the speech in the form of a thank you for following the learning process in class well. Then the teacher added a greeting to enjoy lunch for the students. Students respond well to begin preparing to tidy up their desk for rest. So from its use, the teacher's speech has an expressive speech act function.

e) Declaration Speech Act

(3-5) Data MD

The purpose of data speech 3, a declarative speech act, is to impose a sentence. This punishment is expressed through verbal speech in interactions that contain communication between the teacher and students in the class. Speech data in this study that revealed the function of imposing a sentence as follows.

Teacher : OK, Jeje if you need time, silakan di luar tertawa, I'll wait. (OK, Jeje if you need time, please laugh outside, I will wait)

The teacher's speech in the learning process is not only informative but the statement expresses its statement that the success of the implementer appears in its conformity to the reality of the action. The speech delivered by the teacher is in accordance with the reality of the sentence sentenced to a student. The reality of the effects caused by the speech can be seen from the reaction of students to leave the classroom. In this case the teacher gives a penalty to give a deterrent effect to the student. So from its use, the teacher's speech has a declaration of speech acts.

4. Conclusion

This research analyzes the speech acts from three aspects, namely the types of speech acts, the forms of speech acts, and the speech acts used by the teacher in the learning process at Canggü Community School. The data in this study were analyzed using speech act type theory proposed by Austin (1962), speech act form theory proposed by Wijana & Putu (2004), and speech act function theory proposed by Searle (1969). From the results of this study it can be concluded as follows.

Research conducted shows that the types of speech acts that appear in the learning process at Canggü Community School are locus speech acts, illocutionary speech acts, and perlocutionary speech acts. The locus speech act contained in the learning process shows the speech which contains information about the material delivered by the teacher as a speaker to the speech partner, namely students. Illocutionary speech acts in the learning process indicate the intent of the teacher's implied speech so that students follow the instructions given in the learning process. At the same time, the act of speech elocution in the learning process is told by the teacher so that students, as speech partners, respond to each assignment or exam. Every response given by a student can be in the form of speech or action.

The speech acts in declarative, interrogative, and imperative modes that appear in the teacher's speech in the learning process at Canggü Community School. Declarative speech acts found in this study contain speech used to convey information by the teacher to students. Interrogative speech acts in this study contain utterances conventionally used to ask questions to get information from the teacher in class. While in imperative speech acts, the teacher conveys utterances that are generally used to give orders. The forms of teacher speech acts found in the learning process at Canggü Community School are five declarative utterances (22 %), 11 interrogative utterances (48 %), and seven imperative utterances (30 %).

The researcher found that the speech acts delivered by the teacher in the learning process can be classified by assertive, directive, commissive, expressive, and declarative categories. Assertive speech acts in this study contain teacher utterances that state proposing, complaining, and submitting opinions. The directive speech acts found in this study stated to govern, demand, and give advice. Commissive speech acts found in this study contain teacher utterances in the form of offering and promising something. Expressive speech acts delivered by the teacher during the learning process expressing gratitude, congratulating, and criticizing. Declarative speech acts found in this research are in the form of utterances stating names, and sentencing. Speech act functions found in the learning process at Canggü Community School, namely: 6 assertive utterances (22 %), ten directive utterances (37 %), three commissive utterances (11 %), five expressive utterances (19 %), and three declarative utterances (11 %).

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